

Thermal stresses in the $\text{Nd}_2\text{Fe}_{14}\text{B}$ polycrystal system with grain boundary phase

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Strain in the range of 1.2 % has been measured in $\text{Nd}_2\text{Fe}_{14}\text{B}$ sintered magnets [1] near grain boundaries. Such strains may reduce the magnetocrystalline anisotropy by around 10 percent and in turn reduce the coercive field [2].

The present study focuses on the evaluation of residual stresses caused by temperature changes in production and recycling of $\text{Nd}_2\text{Fe}_{14}\text{B}$ permanent magnets. Using a mechanistic approach we derive an analytical solution, for the contact of two infinitely large crystals (Fig. 1). This is equivalent to a system of alternating plates of two materials with different thickness and constant period of alternation. For checking the analytical solutions, modelling has been performed by the FEM [3]. Strain values were measured in the stationary area. We computed the strain for different systems such as direct contact of two $\text{Nd}_2\text{Fe}_{14}\text{B}$ grains at different orientations and $\text{Nd}_2\text{Fe}_{14}\text{B}$ – Cu interfaces. The results of the analytical calculation and simulation have shown satisfactory matching.

Figure 1: Two-crystal system: schematics and modelling [3]

For the model system, the computed thermal strains are in the order of 0.1% to 0.2%, which is a factor of 10 smaller than the maximum strain measured in [1]. However, strain hot spots may occur at triple junctions [4] not considered in the current analysis. Nevertheless, our work shows the impact of different scenarios on the stress level. In the system of two differently oriented identical $\text{Nd}_2\text{Fe}_{14}\text{B}$ crystals the maximum residual thermal stresses are 330 MPa as the temperature changes by 500 K. Assuming a Cu grain boundary phase, which may be achieved in recycled NdFeB magnets, the maximum stresses in $\text{Nd}_2\text{Fe}_{14}\text{B}$ reduces to 11 MPa. The use of grain boundary materials with low stiffness and small thickness should significantly reduce the level of residual thermal stresses in magnetic crystals.

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